
MEDIA ETHICS IN INDIA RESTORATION OF PRESS FREEDOM POST EMERGENCY AND RISE OF MEDIA CAPITALISM**Mithun Madhava**

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ABSTRACT

Media is an important institution in a Democracy. Media plays the role of watchdog in any society. The Study focuses on Post Emergency Era in India. It analyses the restoration of press freedom and subsequent strengthening of Indian print media especially the regional language press. The paper examines the combination of factors which led to rise of Media Capitalism in India. Today the media stands as a profitable business generating immense returns and treated as a viable stand-alone business. The consequences of blind profit making may have impacted Indian Democracy. Thus, it is crucial as a society to safeguard the Indian media and to protect the working model of Democracy.

Keywords: Restoration of press freedom, role of media, Media Ethics, Democracy, Media Capitalism.

INTRODUCTION

The News media plays an important role in any Democracy and society. India is the largest democracy in the world and newspapers have always played a crucial role in fostering and strengthening democratic values in Indian Society. Media is the fourth pillar of democracy keeping a watch on Executive Judiciary and Legislature. This role often puts the media in conflict with the government of the day. This paper attempts to analyse the restoration of Democracy in India post emergency and the growth of media in the late seventies and eighties. The Emergency was a challenging period for Indian press and it faced direct suppression by the Indira government. The objective of the research paper is to throw light on the post emergency situation and the importance of media in plural society like India. For writing this research paper Historical, Analytical and comparative method has been adopted to trace the media behaviour emergency and post emergency situation.

Emergency and Media

In India, "the Emergency" refers to a 21-month period from 1975 to 1977 when Prime Minister Indira Gandhi had a state of emergency declared across the country. On 25th June 1975 the proclamation of emergency was issued by President Fakhruddin Ali Ahmed under article 352 of the constitution. On the night of 25th June 1975 power supply was cut off to New Delhi's street of major dailies Bahadur Shah Zafar-Marg and effectively censored the next morning's elite English Language newspapers.

The fundamental rights of the Indian people were suspended, and strict controls were imposed on freedom of speech and press. With the imposition of emergency, a host of repressive measures was introduced, and for the first time in India pre-censorship was imposed by promulgating a Censorship Order dated 26th June 1975 under Rule 48 of the Defence of India Rules (DIR), 1971. As a result of the Censorship Order, no news, comment, rumour or other report relating to any action taken under certain provisions of the DIR, could be published unless it was previously submitted to Censor (called authorised officer) for his scrutiny and his permission was obtained.

Government used police forces across the country to place thousands of protestors and strike leaders under preventive detention. Prominent Leaders of Opposition Parties like Vijayaraje Scindia, Jayaprakash Narayan, Raj Narain, Morarji Desai, Charan Singh, Atal Bihari Vajpayee, Lal Krishna Advani, Arun Jaitley were arrested under the provisions of MISA(Maintenance of Internal Security Act). During the emergency Indira Gandhi had a firm grip on the Indian mass media. This was especially true since radio and television in India are government owned and operated.

She used at least three methods in manipulating the newspapers:

- (1) Allocation of government advertising;
- (2) Shotgun merger of the news agencies and
- (3) Use of fear-arousal techniques on newspaper publishers, journalists and individual shareholders.

Kuldip Nayyar Editor of Delhi edition of Statesman was arrested under the provisions of MISA Act. The response of the Indian press towards emergency was one of surrender and fear.

Media Response to Emergency Proclamation

Times of India, Hindustan times and The Hindu accepted the official government stance and toed the line. Prominent Editors like Russi Karanjia of the Blitz and Khushwant Singh of Illustrated weekly of the Times Group supported the Emergency. During censorship, most of the nation's domestic dailies, however, gave up the battle for press freedom. Their pages were "filled with fawning accounts of national events, flattering pictures of Gandhi and her ambitious son, and not coincidentally, lucrative government advertising. But two tough, prominent publishers of English- language dailies, The Indian Express and The Statesman, fought courageously against Indira Gandhi's oppression of the Indian press. The Indian Express Delhi edition on June 28, 1975 carried a blank first editorial and the Financial Express reproduced in large type Rabindranath Tagore's poem "where the mind is without fear and the head held high" concluding with the prayer "Into that heaven of freedom, my Father, let my country awake."

In Mumbai Himmat a small local weekly edited by Rajmohan Gandhi left its editorial page blank. Of course, even a more valiant attitude was shown by independent, small journals like Sadhana (Marathi), Bhoomiputra (Gujrati), Seminar (a monthly journal) and Opinion (a weekly sheet). The Indian Express group led by its valiant editor and owner Ramnath Goenka opposed emergency tooth and nail. He received the highest attention from the Indira government and was greatly targeted. The paper was strangled of government advertising support faced litigation and tax raids by government agencies. Undeterred it reported on many violations during emergency including slum demolitions and forced family planning programmes. Pre-censorship was imposed on all editions of Indian Express on August 16, 1976. Goenka filed a petition against it in the Bombay High Court and the Government withdrew its order on September 30, 1976. The Government then issued orders to all departments and public sector corporations not to advertise in any of the Indian Express group of news papers. The Statesman, a private limited company, followed the Indian Express. It's overpowering Managing Director, C.R. Irani, and Chairman of the board, N.A. Palkhiwala, the famous lawyer, both on the board of trustees of the paper, kept the paper within the law but saw that it took as much advantage as possible. The Statesman had its government advertisement suspended and it was only after the elections that the ban was removed.

End of Emergency

On 18 January 1977, Indira Gandhi called fresh elections for March and released all political prisoners though the Emergency officially ended on 23 March 1977. Press Censorship was also ended. In the Lok Sabha elections, held in March 1977, Mrs. Gandhi and Sanjay Gandhi her son both lost their Lok Sabha seats, as did all the Congress Candidates in Northern states such as Bihar and Uttar Pradesh. The Congress was reduced to just 153 seats, 92 of which were from four of the southern states. The Janata Party's 298 seats and its allies' 47 seats (out of a total 542) gave it a massive majority. Morarji Desai became the first non-Congress Prime Minister of India. With the relaxation in censorship provisions on the eve of elections to the 6th Lok Sabha in 1977, the media got the breathing space, and eventually bounced back as a watchdog of democracy. The pro-government newspapers continued to support the government however they were also able to provide space to opposition parties and the newly formed Janata party.

The new Janata regime came to power because of the anti-democratic policies and decisions of the government of Mrs Indira Gandhi. During the campaign JP and other leaders of the anti-emergency regime made pledges to the electorate that they would restore fundamental rights, civil liberties, and freedom of the press as soon as they achieved the

leadership of the nation. Therefore, the principal task of the newly formed Janta Government was to repeal legislation damaging to the Fundamental Rights and to restore a democratic constitution through a comprehensive amendment (Austin, 1999:409). On April 9, 1977 the Prevention of Publication of Objectionable Matters Act was repealed. The Parliamentary Proceedings (Protection Of Publication) Act was not only re-enacted restoring the privilege but was buttressed and expanded, giving it Constitutional protection, by inserting Article 361 A in the constitution by the constitution (44th Amendment) Act, 1978. (Bakshi, 2009:298) Along with this the Press Council Act was passed and the Press Council was revived.

Restoration of Press Freedom

Soon after the government of Prime Minister Morarji Desai (popularly known as "Janata Party" government) took over the political power in India, it announced three distinct steps toward restoring freedom of the Indian mass media. These were: (1) to establish a committee to study misuse of mass media during the internal emergency; (2) to establish a working group to study the question of converting All India Radio and Doordarshan (television) into autonomous institutions; and (3) to establish a committee to study the feasibility of restructuring the existing news agency (Samachar). (Singh, 1980:43) On May 21, 1977, a one-man committee was established; the committee was headed by Mr. K. K. Das, a former secretary of the Ministry of Information

and Broadcasting, Government of India. The committee was asked to look into the following matters: misuse of censorship provisions; harassment of journalists; allegations in regard to certification of films; manipulation of mass media

The post-emergency government of India under the prime ministership of Mr Morarji Desai decided to constitute an inquiry commission to reveal the facts and figures regarding the misuses and abuses of the authority of state during the internal emergency. The role of the Inquiry Commission was crucial so the government has decided to appoint a former Chief Justice of the Apex Court of India as the head of the Inquiry Commission. Therefore, Shah Commission was a commission of inquiry appointed by the newly formed Janata Party Government in 1977 to inquire into the excesses committed by the Government of Mrs Gandhi during the Internal Emergency (1975-77). It was headed by Justice J. C Shah, A former chief Justice of India (Sen, 2002:139).

The commission was to report by 31 December 1977, but was later given an extension to 30 June 1978 (Kritz & Mandela, 1995: 236). Justice Shah was insistent that the commission should complete its work quickly rather than dragging on endlessly like other commissions (Sen, 2002:139). He set a deadline of 3 July 1977 as the last date on which complaints could be filed. Complaints were categorized, with some being investigated by commission staff and the more important ones being handled through open hearings (Sen, 2002:140).

The first interim report was submitted on 11 March 1978, 149 dealing with the lead-up to the declaration of the Emergency and the way in which the press was prevented from speaking out. The second interim report discussed police actions and the role of Sanjay Gandhi at the Turkman Gate incident in which police fired on a crowd of people protesting against demolition of their houses. The final report was issued on 6 August 1978 and covered prison conditions, torture and family planning atrocities. (Anant, 2010:205) Concerning the circumstances in which the emergency was proclaimed, the commission found that there was no economic crisis and no crisis of law and order (Sen, 2002:140-141).

The commission decided that the decision to impose Emergency was made by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi alone, without consulting her cabinet colleagues, and was not justified. Her arrest and long-running trial, gained her great sympathy from many people who had feared her as a tyrant just two years earlier. Mrs. Gandhi succeeded in defying both the courts and the government over the alleged improprieties committed even before the emergency. She began giving speeches again, tacitly apologizing for "mistakes" made during the Emergency, thus proceeding with her political comeback in the backdrop of the crumbling rule of the Janata party. This set up the stage for the 1980 elections, which brought Indira Gandhi back to office (Desai, 1977:25). The Emergency was endorsed by Vinoba Bhave (who called it Anushasan parva or Time for discipline) and Mother Teresa. Pioneer industrialist J. R. D Tata, and writer Khushwant Singh were among the other prominent supporters. Some have argued that India badly needed economic recovery after the Indo-Pak war had strained the exchequer. Indira's 20-point economic program increased agricultural production, manufacturing activity, exports and foreign reserves. The national economy achieved high levels of growth and investment, and as strikes were non-existent, productivity increased rapidly. In the General Elections of 1980 the Congress party and Mrs Gandhi made a come back winning the elections and capturing power. However Mrs Gandhi's attitude towards the press was cautious and she did not curb the freedom of the press once again.

The measures taken by the Janata party government strengthened Democracy in India. It also led to the growth of Indian Print media especially the regional newspapers.

The Rise of Media Capitalism.

As the emergency was lifted in India and Press freedom was restored India saw a no of media entrepreneurs and capitalists who developed the media business. Prominent amongst them were Ramoji Rao who founded Enadu Telugu newspaper and Vinit Jain the promoter of Times of India. Before Emergency Media businesses in India were not very profitable. Indian media was dominated by English language newspapers. Television and radio were completely under Government control. Post Emergency Regional language newspapers began to increase their circulation. For decade in the eighties Malayalam newspaper Malayala Manorama was the largest selling newspaper in India selling more than a million copies. Post Emergency period saw the rise of media capitalism due to unshackling of media controls and smart entrepreneurship.

The transformation of publishing into a business began post-1977, after the Emergency was lifted. The Janata government, which came to power in the post-Emergency elections, repealed most of the regressive laws. Across the country, people bought more newspapers because they wanted to know what had happened in the preceding months. In the essays and the subsequent book, Robin Jeffrey traces the growth of the Indian language press from 1977 to 1999. He puts it down to three factors:

- A. The growth of literacy,
- B. The rise of capitalism and
- C. The spread of technology.

The last refers to advances in offset printing coupled with communications technology that allowed the use of facsimile or satellite editions. In three years - between the depths of the “emergency” in 1976 and 1979, the year before Mrs Gandhi returned to power newspaper circulations rose 40 per cent for daily newspapers and 34 per cent for periodicals. The sales of Hindi dailies surpassed those of English for the first time in 1979. Such increases were notable, but they only hinted at the profound changes within the newspaper industry. The immense curiosity created by the “emergency” generated a market for anyone with a story to tell and a press to print it on. And the millions of literate people, able and eager to pay to read what happened to themselves and their neighbours, constituted a growing force whose preoccupations and goals provided subjects for journalists. People wanted to read about themselves.

Ramoji Rao launched the Enadu a newspaper for Andhra Pradesh that would bring local news to readers. He already had several successful businesses—Margadarsi Chit Fund, Priya Pickle as well as a number of hotels. When he decided to launch a newspaper from Visakhapatnam in 1974, Indian Express’ Andhra Prabha was the leader with 74,000 copies. The second newspaper, Andhra Patrika, was losing circulation. In 1975, when Rao's Enadu was launched in Hyderabad, it divided the city into target areas, recruited delivery boys three months before publication and gave away the newspaper free for a week. In each subsequent town that it was launched (Tirupati, Ananthapur, Karimnagar and others), the newspaper was marketed in an interesting new way. By 1978, within four years of its launch, Enadu had surpassed Andhra Prabha's circulation. By 1995, two rivals — Andhra Patrika and Udayam—had folded up and Enadu commanded 75 per cent of the audited circulation of Telugu dailies.

Meanwhile, in 1979, Mumbai saw the launch of its first successful afternoon daily, Mid-Day, which eventually led to the closure of TOI's Evening News. The 16-page tabloid was priced at 25 paise. It was successes such as Mid-Day and Enadu that pushed other proprietors to invest in offset technology, satellite editions and relook their distribution methods to boost circulation. The old set of proprietors finally began to view their publications as a business. It seems rather obvious today but remember that we are talking about a time when editorial and circulation did not work in conjunction, and the marketing department did not exist. There was seemingly no connection between what people wanted to read and how the product was to be marketed or sold.

The biggest change in the ‘businesses of publishing came with the entry of the reclusive Samir Jain as the owner and Publisher of Times of India. The story of how he used simple marketing principles and good business sense to transform his down-in-the-dumps publishing company into a profit-spewing machine is well documented. From ₹47 million in 1987–1988, BCCL's profit before tax jumped to ₹1.3 billion on revenues of ₹4.79 billion in the 12 months by the end of July 1994.

BCCL is now the print arm of the estimated ₹10-billion Times Group which also owns TV, radio and internet brands. In the financial year of 2018–2019, it made revenues of ₹70 billion and a massive ₹9 billion in profit after tax. ‘The Jains were the first to look at return on investment, pricing, promotion.

Many Hindi dailies such as Dainik Bhaskar, Dainik Jagran and Amar Ujala borrowed from the TOI book. ‘In the 1990s, regional newspapers like the Malayala Manorama and Anand Bazar

Patrika and Enadu saw huge profits due to business expansion. G. Krishnan, the former CEO of TV Today Network and an old TOI hand, remarked, ‘Till then, the market was driving media; by the late 1980s, media started driving the market’.

Through his utter devotion to the bottom line, Jain managed to bring about a mindset change desperately needed at that point. His timing was impeccable. It was not only Jain's example that other newspaper proprietors were following. Post-liberalization opportunities were springing up for them. By 1992, both news-print and printing machinery were placed under the open general licence, making their import easier. Add to it one other fact. Advertising too was changing hands with multinational corporations taking charge of the ad business. The foreign agencies had a different mindset. It was one that matched Times of India. Thus the post Emergency era saw a freeing of Indian media from government clutches resulting in a high growth of newspaper circulation. This led to increasing profits and expansion of business. As India entered the era of Liberalization and Globalization the Indian media business underwent a great change deeply impacting Indian Democracy.

CONCLUSION

Thus, we can see that the Emergency was a dark phase in Indian Democracy. Freedom of press- an important pillar of democracy was deeply compromised. But the ray of hope was the resistance to emergency put forward by publications like Indian express and Statesman. The post emergency era saw the restoration of Press freedom and encouraged the independence of Print Media. This also created an atmosphere for regional and small newspapers to flourish. As press freedom increased a new breed of media entrepreneurs created great media entities which changed the course of Indian Politics. Thus, the importance of media increased but also led to decreasing values and affected the principles of journalism. To maintain a balanced democracy media has to walk the tight rope between increasing profits and maintaining public welfare.

REFERENCES

1. Ramchandra Guha, Democracy and Dissenters, Penguin Random House, 2016
2. Kuldip Nayar, India: The Critical Years, Vikas, 1971
3. Kuldip Nayar, India After Nehru, Vikas, 1975
4. Bipan Chandra, India After Independence 1947-2000. Penguin Books, 1999
5. Robin Jeffrey, India's Newspaper Revolution, Oxford University Press, 2000
6. Tharoor, S. India: From Midnight to the Millennium, New Delhi: Penguin Books, (1997)
7. Uma Vasudev, Indira Gandhi: Revolution in Restraint, Vikas, 1983
8. Katherine Frank, Indira: The Life of Indira Nehru Gandhi, HarperCollins, 2001.

ARTICLES

1. During the Emergency only three newspapers put up a semblance of resistance, <https://www.indiatoday.in/magazine/nation/story/19770415-during-the-emergency-only-three-newspapers-put-up-a-semblance-of-resistance-818860-2015-04-22>, April 2015.
2. Emergency: The Dark Age of Indian democracy, The Hindu, June 26, 2015. [Http://www.thehindu.com/specials/in-depth/the-emergency-imposed-by-indira-gandhi-government/article7357305.ece](http://www.thehindu.com/specials/in-depth/the-emergency-imposed-by-indira-gandhi-government/article7357305.ece)
3. 40 years on, those 21 months of Emergency, Amrith Lal, Indian Express, July 20, 2015. <http://indianexpress.com/article/explained/40-years-on-those-21-months-of-emergency/>
4. 'Himmat' during the Emergency: When the Press crawled, some refused to even bend, Kalpana Sharma, Scroll.in., June 2015.
5. Indira Gandhi's call of emergency and press censorship in India: the ethical parameters revisited, Dr. Jhumur Ghosh, Global Media Journal – Indian Edition, Winter-Summer Issue/December 2016 – June 2017.
6. In-depth study: The Emergency situation in India and its effects on people, November 30, 1999, India Today, <https://www.indiatoday.in/magazine/india-today-archives/story/19751215-in-depth-study-the-emergency-situation-in-india-and-its-effects-on-the-people-824063-1999-11-30>
7. Why I Supported Emergency, Khushwant Singh, Outlook magazine, July 2000.

Web -Links

1. <https://www.dw.com/en/covid-why-is-india-censoring-media-during-public-health-crisis/a-57353096>
2. <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/covid-19-india-second-wave-how-global-media-covered-health-crisis-7287113/>
3. <https://theprint.in/opinion/no-the-western-media-isnt-biased-in-reporting-indian-covid-heres-why/655101/>
4. <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/mediase/2021/05/07/india-cannot-breathe-is-the-media-choking-it-further/>
5. <https://thewire.in/media/covid-19-india-surge-oxygen-global-media-reports-modi>
6. <https://time.com/6033152/india-media-covid-19/>
7. <https://qz.com/2003051/how-indias-covid-crisis-is-playing-out-in-global-media-coverage/>

8. <https://ijmsweb.com/role-of-mass-media-and-its-impact-on-general-public-during-2019-pandemic-in-north-india-an-online-assessment/> coronavirus-disease-
9. <https://www.dw.com/en/covid-why-is-india-censoring-media-during-public-health-crisis/a-57353096>
10. <https://www.nytimes.com/2021/04/25/business/india-covid19-twitter-facebook.html>
11. <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/covid-19-india-second-wave-how-global-media-covered-health-crisis-7287113/>
12. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/seize-property-of-those-spreading-rumours-upcm/article34404518.ece>
13. <https://thewire.in/government/up-police-lodge-fir-against-lucknow-hospital-which-put-up-oxygen-shortage-notice>
14. <https://www.firstpost.com/india/covid-19-deaths-in-india-local-news-media-uncovers-scale-of-crisis-challenges-official-data-9622721.html>
15. <https://www.npr.org/2021/06/01/1002219151/india-coronavirus-pandemic-response-journalists-criticize-modi>
16. <https://scroll.in/article/992217/as-the-dead-pile-up-in-gujarat-the-states-media-is-on-a-warpath-with-the-government-over-covid-19>
17. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-india-56969086>
18. <https://www.newslaundry.com/2021/04/15/covid-crisis-why-isnt-big-media-holding-the-government-accountable>